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Review Article

Menopausal Hormone Therapy And Its Awareness In Women

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ABSTRACT

Menopause results from cease in ovarian follicular function and marks the end of menstruation. Most women experience menopause between the ages of 40 and 58 years. Hormone replacement therapy (HRT) in the form of estrogen alone or combined estrogen and progesterone formulations has been widely used to treat menopausal symptoms to improve women's quality of life, control their climacteric symptoms and prevent osteoporosis. This study aims to investigate the knowledge and awareness of women towards menopausal hormone replacement therapy and its role in the management of menopause. A cross-sectional observational study was carried out in female population above 18 years of age for 1.5 months. Data was collected using a prestructured online questionnaire using social media platforms. The questionnaire consisted of questions about demographics, menstruation status and about awareness regarding menopause and hormone replacement therapy including menopausal symptoms, HRT treatment options, side effects of HRT etc. 101 participants cooperated with the survey ranging from 18 years and above. 61.4% (n=101) were not in the perimenopausal or menopausal stage, 17.8% were perimenopausal, 7.9% were menopausal and 12.9% were not sure which group they belonged to. Only 18.8% felt well informed about perimenopause/menopause while 66.3% had some knowledge about it and 18.8% are not informed at all. 36.6% had heard of HRT whereas 53.5% had no knowledge about it. This survey demonstrated that the awareness of women about menopausal hormone therapy was not comprehensive and they should be educated more about menopause and use of HRT. Even though some women are aware of HRT as a treatment option; however, a lack of both proper information and positive attitude towards HRT use was noted.

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INTRODUCTION

Perimenopause and menopause have affected approximately one billion women worldwide. Menopause is the permanent cessation of menstruation for 12 months. Once 12 months is reached, the woman will be post-menopause. The perimenopause is an ill-defined time period before the woman has her final period and is often associated with the start of a number of perimenopausal symptoms [1]. They might experience mood disturbances, depression, hot flashes, vasomotor symptoms, recurrent urinary tract infections, vaginal atrophy with alteration of the sexual life and libido, as well as osteoporosis and cardiovascular disease [2]. Globally, there has little formal teaching about the menopause at any stage of a women's life and the media often present the menopause negatively. A consequence of this is that many women have little knowledge or awareness of what can be a very symptomatic life phase [1]. Hormone replacement therapy (HRT) in the form of estrogen alone or combined estrogen and progesterone formulations has been widely used to treat menopausal symptoms to improve women's quality of life, control their climacteric symptoms and prevent osteoporosis [2]. In order to improve the provision of this treatment, it is important to determine the information women have already received from the media and other sources and what their anxieties are. Previous studies of women's knowledge and attitudes have mainly been carried out overseas or have centered around specialist clinics. The aim of this study was therefore to assess the knowledge and awareness of women in relation menopausal hormone therapy in order to improve the provision of this treatment.

OBJECTIVES

To assess the awareness of women towards menopausal hormone replacement therapy and its role in menopause.

METHODOLOGY

Study type: Cross-sectional observational study

Study site: Community based online survey

Sample size:

101 participants based on convenience sampling

Study Duration:

1.5 months

Inclusion criteria:

Female population from the age of 18 and who are willing to participate and voluntarily enrolled were included in the study

Exclusion criteria: Male population was excluded from the study

Data source:

The data was collected through online surveys using structured questionnaires adapted from previous studies and modified to suit our purpose. Questionnaire was prepared in English language including all relevant variables based on the objective of the study.

The tools used have two sections designed to address:

1. Demographic details and,
2. Awareness about menopause and menopausal hormone replacement therapy.

RESULT

A total of 101 women participated in the study and their responses to the questionnaire were analyzed and assessed. The mean age of the women was 32.6 ± 5.3 . The largest category belonged to the age group of 18-24 (53.5%), 20.8% belonged to 25-40, another 20.8% belonged to 41-60 and 5% were aged 60 and above. Majority (54.5%) were undergraduates while 28.7% held a postgraduate degree. 5.9% has primary education, 5% has high school education and 5.9% had higher secondary educational qualification. 42.5% of the participants were students and 31.5% were home makers while rest worked in private sectors, some involved in healthcare and remaining had other occupations. Regarding menstruating status of the participants, 61.4% were not perimenopausal/menopausal. 17.8% are

perimenopausal i.e., they still have periods with sure which category they belonged to. Table 1 perimenopausal symptoms and 7.9% were depicts the demographic data assessed. menopausal/post-menopausal. 12.9% were not

Table 1 demographic data of the sampled women

Demographic details	n (%)
Age	
18-24	54 (53.5%)
25-40	21 (20.8%)
41-60	21 (20.8%)
Above 60	5 (5%)
Educational qualification	
Primary school	6 (5.9%)
High school	5 (5%)
Higher secondary	6 (5.9%)
Undergraduate	55 (54.5%)
Post-graduate	29 (28.7%)
Occupation	
Students	43 (42.5%)
Homemakers	32 (31.5%)
Healthcare sector	4 (3.9%)
Private sector	11 (10.8%)
others	11 (10.8%)
Menstrual status	
Not in the perimenopause/menopause	62 (61.4%)
Perimenopausal	18 (17.8%)
Menopausal	8 (7.9%)
Not sure	13 (12.9%)

When asked about the perimenopausal/menopausal symptoms experienced by women belonging to respective categories (n=37), 32.4% experienced hot flashes, 56.8% had aching joints, 32.4% had irregular periods, 64.9% experienced mood swings, 35.1% had sleep disturbances, 21.6% had memory problems, 18.9% had urinary problems, 37.8% had problems of hair loss and 13.5% experienced vaginal dryness or itching.

Figure 1 Perimenopausal/menopausal symptoms experienced by sampled women

When asked about awareness and information about menopausal hormone therapy, only 18.8% were well informed about perimenopause/menopause while 66.3% had some knowledge about it. 14.9% had no information at

all. A majority of the population who had knowledge sourced it from curriculum (32.6%) and rest from physician, family, friends and also some from social media.

Figure 2 source of information of the participants

As for awareness about menopausal hormone replacement therapy, 54(53.5%, n=101) had not

heard about HRT and therefore were exempted from continuing the survey.

Figure 3 Knowledge about HRT in sampled women

Only 47 among 101(46.5%) participants were knowledgeable about HRT as a treatment option. Among them 38 (80.9%) believed HRT may be considered for treating menopausal symptoms and yet only 2.4% opted for it.

Figure 4 Data assessed about conditions for which HRT can be prescribed

93.6% said that their doctor never suggested them HRT for menopause and thus they have not opted it. 4.3% were not sure if they are currently using HRT. Reasons for not considering HRT is mainly the lack of awareness which made them think therapy is not required (57.1%). 35.7% believed they are too young to start HRT. 72.3% expressed concerns about side effects like vaginal bleeding, breast swelling/cancer, bloating and weight changes.

Figure 5 Reasons for not using HRT for perimenopause/menopause

Table 2 illustrates the distribution of awareness and shows how informed the participants are about menopause and Hormone replacement therapy as a treatment option

Table 2 Distribution of awareness regarding menopausal hormone replacement therapy

Awareness details	n (%)
How informed do you feel about perimenopause/menopause?	
• Very informed	19(18.8%)
• Some knowledge	67(66.3%)
Not informed at all	15(14.9%)
Has your doctor ever suggested you HRT for menopause?	
• Yes	1(2.1%)
• No	44(93.6%)
• Maybe	2(4.3%)
Are you currently using HRT?	
• Yes	1(2.1%)
• No	44(93.6%)
• Maybe	2(4.3%)
if yes, what is the name of your HRT?	norethisterone
If no, give reasons for not using HRT	
• Fear of long-term medication	3(7.1%)
• Risk of side effects	6(14.3%)
• Too old to start HRT	1(2.4%)
• Too young to start HRT	15(35.7%)
• It is not require	24(57.1%)
• Never heard of HRT	2(4.8%)
What do you think are the side effects of HRT?	
• Breast tenderness/swelling	5(10.6%)
• Vaginal bleeding	3(6.4%)
• Bloating	6(12.8%)
• Weight changes	10(21.3%)
• All of the above	34(72.3%)
How long do you think is the optimal duration for HRT treatment for menopause?	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-2yrs • 3-5yrs • Longer than 7 years • Not sure 	3(6.4%) 10(21.3%) 1(2.1%) 33(70.2%)
Which of the following you think are HRT treatment options? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estrogen only • Combined HRT (estrogen and progesterone) • Androgen • Not sure 	4(8.5%) 24(51.1%) - 19(40.4%)
Which of the following route is HRT available in? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tablets • Patches • Injection • Gels • Implants • All of the above • Tablets only 	20(42.6%) 8(17%) 15(31.9%) 2(4.3%) 7(14.9%) 20(42.6%) 4(8.5%)

DISCUSSION

Menopause is a critical transition period in the life of women which affects quality of life. In this study we summarized women's awareness about menopausal hormone therapy and found very little consideration for HRT as a treatment option for perimenopausal/menopausal symptoms. This had mainly to do with the lack of awareness among elderly population about HRT. 93.6% of participants who had knowledge about HRT said that their physician never recommended HRT to them. This is supported by studies by Joyce C Harper et al [1] and MinFang Tao et al [3] which summarizes that many obstetrician-gynecologists have reported they were unlikely to change their prescribing practice following the WHI report on HRT. In the WHI randomized trial, combined hormone therapy increased breast cancer risk and interfered with breast cancer detection, leading to cancers being diagnosed at more advanced stages. However, the preponderance of observational studies has associated combined hormone therapy use with an increase in breast cancers that have favorable characteristics, lower stage, and longer

survival compared with breast cancers diagnosed in nonusers of hormone therapy [4]. In this study, 57.1% feels that treatment is not required for menopausal symptoms and only 2.4% sought clinical advice for perimenopause. Similar findings have been found in a study by Ye Zhu et al [5] in which majority of participants were unaware about the risks and benefits of menopausal hormone therapy. Some believed that menopausal hormone therapy could increase the risk of breast cancer while according to some participants (aged >40years), symptoms of menopause were part of the natural process of ageing and only few participants received treatments for peri-menopausal symptoms. These study results are consistent with other international studies and reported the same symptoms like hot flashes, aching joints, mood swings, irregular periods, sleep disturbances, memory problems etc. A recent study conducted among Saudi women on reported menopausal symptoms revealed that joint and muscle pain (80.7%), physical and mental exhaustion (64.7%), and hot flushes and sweating (47.1%) were the most reported symptom among

midlife women [6]. It is important to note that this study has a limitation since most of the respondents were of a younger age and only a few of them were in the perimenopausal period, suggesting that the sample might not have accurately represented the actual rate of HRT use among the female population.

FUTURE PROSPECTIVES

This study could be extended to a longer duration thereby ensuring better results and power of the study.

CONCLUSION

This survey indicates lack of knowledge and exposure, regarding menopausal hormone therapy and menopause management among various age groups, that in turn might influence the acceptance of HRT among general population. This fact necessitates the need to strengthen the education of women which would be subsequently helpful in disseminating information to general public. Mass media also can serve as an important tool to reach the women and this was proved by Fatemeh Bakouei (2013) on the impact of mass media (television, radio, journals, newspaper, medical doctors, and medical team) among menopausal women to create an awareness, to manage the condition and thereby increasing their quality of life. As long as indications, contraindications and personalization are well controlled, HRT is safe and effective for menopausal women initiating treatment before the age of 60 years. This would help in better menopause management and improving quality of life in the society.

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REFERENCES

1. Harper J, Philips S, Biswakarma R, Yasmin E, Saridogan E, Radhakrishnan S. et al.. An online survey of perimenopausal women to

determine their attitudes and knowledge of menopause. *Women's health*. 2022 Jun; 18:1-26.

2. Salame A, Jaffal M, Khalifeh F, Khalife D, Ghazeeri G. Hormone replacement therapy: Lebanese women's awareness, perception and acceptance. *Obstet gynaecol Int J*. 2020 Jun; 2020(1):1-7.
3. Tao M, Teng Y, Shao H, Wu P, Mills EJ. Knowledge, perception and information about Hormone therapy (HT) among menopausal women: A systematic review and meta-synthesis. *PLoS ONE*. 2011 Sep; 6(9): 1-10.
4. Chlebowski RT, Anderson GL, Gass M, et al. Estrogen Plus Progestin and Breast Cancer Incidence and Mortality in Postmenopausal Women. *JAMA*. 2010 Oct; 304(15):1684-1692.
5. Zhu Y, Yang X, Wang Y, Zhu X. Assessment of knowledge, understanding and awareness of Chinese women and clinical staff towards menopause hormone therapy: a survey study. *J Obstet Gynaecol*. 2023 Jan; 43(1): 1-6.
6. Gayathripriya N, Alasmara N, Omar M, Khalid K, Saleh H, Mohammed H, et al. Menopause awareness, symptoms assessment and MenQol among Bahrain women. *KnE life sciences*. 2018 Oct; 61-77.
7. Gohari H, Shafei S, Ghasemi F. A study on women's health information needs in menopausal age. *BMC womens health*. 2021 Dec; 21(434):1-9.
8. Kadri AZ. Hormone replacement therapy- a survey of perimenopausal women in a community setting. *Br J Gen pract*. 1991 Mar; 41(344): 109-112.

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